

Environmental sequencing provides reasonable estimates of the relative abundance of specific picoeukaryotes

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4 relative abundance of specific picoeukaryotes
5

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19
20 Running title: Correspondence between HTS and cell abundance

21 **Abstract**

22
23 High-throughput sequencing (HTS) is revolutionizing environmental surveys of microbial
24 diversity in the three domains of life by providing detailed information on which taxa are
25 present in microbial assemblages. However, it is still unclear how the relative abundance of
26 specific taxa gathered by HTS correlates with cell abundances. Here, we quantified the
27 relative cell abundance of 6 picoeukaryotic taxa in 13 planktonic samples from six European
28 coastal sites using epifluorescence microscopy on TSA-FISH preparations. These relative
29 abundance values were then compared with HTS data obtained in three separate molecular
30 surveys: 454 sequencing the V4 region of the 18S rDNA using DNA and RNA extracts
31 (DNA-V4 and cDNA-V4), and Illumina sequencing the V9 region (cDNA-V9). The
32 microscopic and molecular signals were generally correlated, indicating that a relative
33 increase in specific 18S rDNA was the result of a large proportion of cells in the given taxa.
34 Despite these positive correlations, the slopes often deviated from 1, precluding a direct
35 translation of sequences to cells. Our data highlighted clear differences depending on nucleic-
36 acid template or the 18S rDNA region targeted. Thus, the molecular signal obtained using
37 cDNA templates was always closer to relative cell abundances, while the V4 and V9 regions
38 gave better results depending on the taxa. Our data supports the quantitative use of HTS data
39 but warn about considering it as direct proxy of cell abundances.

40

41

42 Key words: 18S rDNA, 454 pyrosequencing, FISH, Illumina sequencing, picoeukaryotes,
43 specific abundances

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46 **Importance**

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48 Direct studies on marine picoeukaryotes by epifluorescence microscopy are problematic due
49 to the lack of morphological features, in addition to the limited number and poor resolution of
50 specific phylogenetic probes used in FISH routines. As a consequence, there is an increasing
51 use of molecular methods, including high-throughput sequencing (HTS), to study marine
52 microbial diversity. HTS can provide a detailed picture of the taxa present in a community,
53 and can reveal diversity not evident using other methods, but it is still unclear the meaning of
54 the sequence abundance in a given taxa. Our aim is to investigate the correspondence between
55 the relative HTS signal and relative cell abundances in selected picoeukaryotic taxa.

56 Environmental sequencing provides reasonable estimates of the relative abundance of specific
57 taxa. Better results are obtained when using RNA extracts as templates, while the region of
58 the 18S rDNA influenced differently depending on the taxa assayed.

59

60 **Introduction**

61 Protists are key components of marine ecosystems, being major players in the global
62 respiration and production budgets (1, 2) and playing central roles in marine food webs (3).
63 Despite their importance and ubiquity, it was only during the past decade that environmental
64 studies, based on molecular (i.e. culture-independent) techniques, revealed an unsuspected
65 protist diversity in a large variety of marine ecosystems (4-13). These studies were based on
66 the analysis of 18S ribosomal RNA (rRNA) genes retrieved directly from natural assemblages
67 by PCR amplification, cloning and sequencing. Nowadays, the development and use of high-
68 throughput sequencing tools (HTS), e.g. 454 or Illumina, which produce more than thousands
69 of sequences from a single sample, has revolutionized the field, allowing deeper assessments
70 of diversity (14), as well as better estimates of specific relative abundances. One of the main
71 challenges of this approach, however, is to understand the correspondence between the
72 relative abundances of sequences and cells. That is, how close is the specific diversity
73 detected in molecular surveys to the true species composition of natural assemblages.

74 Few studies have analyzed the relationship between direct microscopic inspections
75 and sequencing data in protists. One of the first studies compared cloning and sequencing
76 results with an accurate list of protists species (5-100 μm size range) identified by microscopy
77 (15). In that case, as the sequencing effort was very limited (less than 100 clones), few of the
78 protists identified by morphology were detected in the sequencing set. In addition, the few
79 sequences obtained did not represent the dominant observed species, a clear sign of the biases
80 in this molecular approach. More recent comparative studies used HTS, therefore were not
81 limited by the sequencing effort, but focused on specific taxa, in particular marine and
82 freshwater ciliates (2, 16-18). Ciliate species have the advantage of having conspicuous
83 morphological traits that allow proper identification by inverted microscopy. In most cases,
84 the same species were found in microscopic and molecular datasets, but the relative

85 abundance of sequences and morphotypes were not in agreement, so each approach revealed a
86 different community structure. Other studies prepared mock communities and the results
87 obtained were similar: all individual taxa were detected, but the relative proportion of
88 sequence types was different from cell mixes (19, 20). Overall, the popularization of HTS
89 now allows a high-resolution exploration of protist richness present in natural samples, yet
90 when it comes to evenness, the picture obtained is still limited.

91 Among protists, picoeukaryotes (protists up to 3 μm in size) are known to be very
92 diverse, widely distributed, and ecologically important in the marine plankton realm (21).
93 Picoeukaryotes are counted as a group by epifluorescence microscopy using a general DNA
94 stain (22) or by flow cytometry (23), but due to their small size and lack of morphological
95 traits (24) they cannot be taxonomically identified by these tools. This can be achieved with
96 FISH (Fluorescence *in situ* Hybridization), which enables the visualization and quantification
97 of specific cells in natural assemblages by using oligonucleotide probes as phylogenetic stains
98 (25). FISH has served to identify the cells from novel environmental clades (11, 26, 27), and
99 has been applied in a few marine surveys (28-31). But this approach is relatively time
100 consuming and targets only one taxon at a time.

101 In this study, we assess the feasibility of using HTS data as a quantitative metric in
102 picoeukaryote diversity studies, by comparing relative HTS read abundances with relative
103 FISH cell counts in selected picoeukaryotic taxa. Differently to the previous studies in which
104 a single taxa (ciliates) or artificial communities were analyzed, here we focus in a set of
105 highly divergent lineages found in geographically separated and unrelated microbial
106 assemblages. Any pattern emerging from this heterogeneous and noisy dataset is expected to
107 be rather robust. We also investigate if there is a difference in community composition
108 assessed by using environmental DNA or RNA extracts as templates (DNA and cDNA reads,
109 respectively), sequencing different regions of the 18S rDNA (V4 versus V9), or using

110 different HTS platforms (454 versus Illumina). To address these questions we used published
111 sequencing datasets from several European coastal samples (Massana *et al.*, 2015 for
112 DNA/cDNA-V4 (32) and Logares *et al.*, 2014 for cDNA-V9 (33)) and chose 6 picoeukaryote
113 taxa (<3 µm) for which we had specific FISH probes for quantification.

114

115 **Materials and Methods**

116 *Sampling*

117 Samples were taken during the BioMarKs project (<http://www.biomarks.org>) in six
118 European coastal sites: Blanes (Spain, 41° 40' N, 2° 48' E), Gijon (Spain, 43° 40' N; 5° 35'
119 W), Naples (Italy, 40° 48' N, 14° 15' E), Oslo (Norway, 59° 16' N, 10° 43' E), Roscoff
120 (France, 48° 46' N, 3° 57' W) and Varna (Bulgaria, 43°10' N, 28° 50' E) (Table 1). Seawater
121 was collected with Niskin bottles attached to a CTD (conductivity-temperature-depth) rosette
122 at surface and deep chlorophyll maximum (DCM) depths. For molecular surveys, ~20 L of
123 seawater was pre-filtered through a 20 µm metallic mesh and then sequentially filtered
124 through 3 µm and 0.8 µm polycarbonate filters (142 mm diameter). The later filter contained
125 the picoplankton (0.8-3 µm size fraction) and was flash-frozen and stored at -80°C. The
126 filtration time was less than 30 minutes to avoid RNA degradation.

127 Unfiltered seawater was taken for direct cell counts. For total microscopic counts,
128 seawater samples were fixed with glutaraldehyde (1% final concentration) and left for 1-24 h
129 at 4°C. Then, aliquotes of 20 ml were filtered through 0.6 µm polycarbonate black filters and
130 stained with DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole, 5 µg ml⁻¹). Filters were mounted on a slide
131 and stored at -20°C until processed. For TSA-FISH (Tyramide Signal Amplification-
132 Fluorescent *in situ* Hybridization) specific counts, aliquotes of 100 ml were fixed with filtered

133 formaldehyde (3.7% final concentration), incubated for 1-24 h in the dark at 4°C and filtered
134 through 0.6 µm polycarbonate filters (25 mm diameter). Filters were kept at -80°C until
135 processed. For flow cytometry counting of photosynthetic picoeukaryotes, aliquotes of 1.5 ml
136 were fixed with a mix of paraformaldehyde/glutaraldehyde (1%/0.25% final concentrations),
137 frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until processed.

138 ***Picoeukaryote cell abundance by DAPI staining and flow cytometry***

139 Total cell abundance of picoeukaryotes was estimated in DAPI-stained filters. Cells
140 were counted with an epifluorescence microscope (Olympus BX61) at 1000X under UV
141 excitation, changing to blue light excitation to verify the presence or absence of chlorophyll
142 autofluorescence (phototrophic and heterotrophic cells, respectively). A transect of about 13
143 mm was inspected and cells were classified in size classes: 2 µm, 3 µm, 4 µm, 5 µm and >5
144 µm. All data reported in the study refers to cells within the two smaller size classes (2-3 µm),
145 which account on average for 82% of the cells.

146 Cell abundance of photosynthetic picoeukaryotes was determined in a FACSort flow
147 cytometer by using the red fluorescence signal (chlorophyll) after exciting in a 488 nm laser
148 and the SSC (side-scattered light) of each particle. Fluorescent microspheres (0.95 µm beads)
149 were added as an internal standard (at 10⁵ beads ml⁻¹). Data was acquired for 2-4 minutes with
150 a flow rate of 50 to 100 µl min⁻¹ using the settings previously described (34).

151 ***Cell abundance of specific picoeukaryote taxa by TSA-FISH***

152 The specific oligonucleotide probes used targeted several picoeukaryote taxa: NS4 and
153 NS7 targeted the uncultured clades MAST-4 and MAST-7; CRN02 and MICRO01 the
154 species *Minorisa minuta* and *Micromonas* spp.; PELA01 the class Pelagophyceae; and
155 ALV01 the environmental clade MALV-II (Table 2). These probes have been published in

156 other studies (see Table 2 for references) except NS7. Probe NS7 was designed here with
157 ARB (35) and targeted 91% of the 192 sequences from MAST-7 available in GenBank, had 1
158 mismatch with the remaining MAST-7 sequences, and at least 2 central mismatches with non-
159 target sequences. Probe NS7 gave better signal when combined with oligonucleotide helpers
160 contiguous to the probe region (NS7-HelperA: AACCAACAAAATAGCAC; NS7-HelperB:
161 CCCAACTATCCCTATTAA) that were added in the hybridization buffer at same
162 concentration than the probe. We tested a range of formamide concentration to find the best
163 hybridization condition, and checked that the probe gave negative signal with a variety of
164 non-target cultures. Finally, a probe targeting all eukaryotes (EUK502, 36) was also used. All
165 probes were labeled with horseradish peroxidase (HRP).

166 Hybridizations were performed as previously described (37). Filter pieces (about 1/10)
167 of the 0.6 μm polycarbonate filters were covered with 20 μl of hybridization buffer (40%
168 deionized formamide [except 30% for probe CNR01], 0.9 M NaCl, 20 mM Tris-HCl [pH 8],
169 0.01% sodium dodecyl sulfate [SDS]) and 2 μl of HRP-labeled probes (stock at 50 $\text{ng } \mu\text{l}^{-1}$),
170 and incubated overnight at 35°C. After the hybridization, filter pieces were washed twice for
171 10 min at 37°C with a washing buffer (37 mM NaCl [74mM NaCl when hybridizing with
172 20% formamide], 5 mM EDTA, 0.01% SDS, 20mM Tris-HCl [pH 8]). Tyramide signal
173 amplification (TSA) was carried out in a solution (1x PBS, 2 M NaCl, 1 mg ml^{-1} blocking
174 reagent, 100 mg ml^{-1} dextran sulfate, 0.0015% H_2O_2) containing Alexa 488-labeled tyramide
175 ($4 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), by incubating in the dark at room temperature for 30-60 min. Filter pieces were
176 transferred twice to a phosphate buffer (PBS) bath in order to stop the enzymatic reaction and
177 air dried at room temperature. Cells were countersained with DAPI ($5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and filter
178 pieces were mounted on a slide. Targeted FISH cells were counted by epifluorescence under
179 blue light excitation and checked with UV radiation (DAPI staining) for the presence of the
180 nucleus. Cells labeled with the probe EUK502 were counted using the same size classes as for

181 DAPI counts. Data reported refers to cells of 2-3 μm , which account on average for 84% of
182 the cells.

183 ***High-throughput sequencing by 454 and Illumina***

184 HTS data derives from previously published papers taken during the BioMarKs
185 project (<http://www.biomarks.org/>). Total DNA and RNA from 13 picoplankton samples were
186 extracted simultaneously from the same filter. For RNA extracts, contaminating DNA was
187 removed and RNA was immediately reverse transcribed to cDNA. Data for the 454
188 sequencing derives from Massana *et al.* (32) and used the eukaryotic universal primers
189 TAREuk454FWD1 and TAREukREV3 (38), which amplified the V4 region of the 18S rDNA
190 (~380 bp). Amplicon sequencing from DNA and cDNA templates was carried out on a 454
191 GS FLX Titanium system (454 Life Sciences, USA) in Genoscope
192 (<http://www.genoscope.cns.fr>, France). The complete sequencing dataset is available at the
193 European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) under the accession number PRJEB9133
194 (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/data/view/PRJEB9133>). Data for the Illumina sequencing derives
195 from Logares *et al.* (33) and used the eukaryotic universal primers 1398f and 1510r (39),
196 which amplified the V9 region of the 18S rDNA (~130 bp). Paired-end 100 bp sequencing
197 was performed using a Genome Analyzer Iix (GAIIx) system located at Genoscope. Only
198 RNA (cDNA) samples were sequenced with Illumina. Sequences are publicly available at
199 MG-RAST (<http://metagenomics.anl.gov>) under accession numbers 4549958.3, 4549965.3,
200 4549959.3, 4549945.3, 4549943.3, 4549927.3, 4549941.3, 4549954.3, 4549922.3.

201 ***Sequence analysis of HTS reads***

202 HTS reads by 454 and Illumina were quality checked following similar criteria as
203 detailed in the original papers (32, 33). After the quality control, chimera detection was run
204 with UCHIME (40) and ChimeraSlayer (41) using SILVA108 and PR² (42) as reference

205 databases. The final curated reads were clustered into OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units)
206 by using UCLUST 1.2.22 (43) with similarity thresholds of 97% for V4-reads and 95% for
207 V9-reads. Representative reads of each OTU were taxonomically classified by using BLAST
208 against SILVA108, PR² and a marine microeukaryote database (44). After the taxonomic
209 assignment, metazoan OTUs were removed. From the complete OTU tables for 454 (32) and
210 Illumina datasets (33), the samples targeting the picoplankton were extracted: 13 samples for
211 DNA-V4, 13 samples for cDNA-V4 and 9 samples for cDNA-V9. Then, OTUs corresponding
212 to taxa typically larger than 3 μm (Dinophyceae, Ciliophora, Acantharia, Diatomea,
213 Polycystinea, Raphidophyceae, Ulvophyceae, Rodophyta and Xanthophyceae; in this order
214 of relative abundance) were removed. These groups accounted for 8.0% to 87.7% (average of
215 36.9%) of the 454 dataset and 11.5% to 73.5% (average of 33.9%) of the Illumina dataset.
216 The read number in the final OTU tables of picoeukaryotes was 110,258 for DNA-V4, 77,554
217 for cDNA-V4 and 1,753,600 for cDNA-V9.

218 The relative abundance of the picoeukaryotic groups of interest was retrieved from
219 these taxonomically classified OTU tables, by dividing the number of reads of the specific
220 OTUs corresponding to the groups of interest by the total number of reads in the sample.
221 Altogether, the six taxa of interest accounted for 36.4% of the DNA-V4 reads, 23.5% of the
222 cDNA-V4 reads, and 32.4% of the cDNA-V9 reads. Besides the taxonomic classification of
223 OTUs in the OTU table, we did an additional classification of the unclustered 454 and
224 Illumina reads, to obtain the raw reads for probe checking (see results) and to double-check
225 the taxonomic classification. For this second classification we downloaded GenBank
226 sequences representative of each picoeukaryotic group of interest and used this specific taxa-
227 database to retrieve HTS reads by local BLAST (sequence similarity >97%).

228

229 **Results**

230 *An overview of total picoeukaryote counts in marine coastal waters*

231 We estimated the total cell abundance of picoeukaryotes by epifluorescence
232 microscopy and flow cytometry in 13 planktonic samples taken in six geographically
233 separated European coastal sites and different depths (Table 1). Total picoeukaryote counts
234 (cells $<3 \mu\text{m}$) by epifluorescence microscopy of DAPI-stained samples revealed a wide range
235 of cell abundances, from 3,139 cells ml^{-1} in Naples-2010 DCM to 24,346 cells ml^{-1} in Oslo-
236 2010 DCM (average of 10,500 cells ml^{-1} in all samples). Phototrophic and heterotrophic cells
237 were differentiated while counting the DAPI samples. The total abundance of phototrophic
238 cells was generally higher than heterotrophic cells (average of 8,200 and 2,400 cells ml^{-1} ,
239 respectively), with the exception of Naples-2010 Surface, where both assemblages have
240 similar abundances. In some cases (Blanes, Oslo-2010 DCM, Roscoff and Varna DCM)
241 phototrophic cells were >6 times more abundant than heterotrophic cells. Counts of
242 phototrophic picoeukaryotes obtained by flow cytometry correlated well with the microscopic
243 counts in the 10 samples analyzed (linear slope = 0.74, Pearson's $r = 0.9$, $P < 0.001$). When
244 forcing the regression line to intercept at 0, the slope was 0.90.

245 The general eukaryotic probe EUK502 was also used to estimate total picoeukaryotic
246 abundance. Cell counts by TSA-FISH were always lower than DAPI counts (60% on average)
247 (Fig. 1). In fact, the sample with the highest total cell abundance was different if estimated by
248 DAPI (Oslo-2010 DCM) or by TSA-FISH (Oslo-2009 Surface). The regression between both
249 datasets was significant, but with a slope very distant from 1 (linear slope = 0.26, Pearson's r
250 = 0.74, $P < 0.05$). When forcing the line to intercept at 0, the slope was still very low, 0.43.
251 There was some tendency to this discrepancy, as TSA-FISH seemed to underestimate more
252 severely the total cell counts in samples dominated by very small cells. Clearly, DAPI counts

253 provided a better estimate of total picoeukaryotic abundance than TSA-FISH counts, and
254 therefore DAPI counts were used to calculate the relative cell abundances of each of the 6
255 specific picoeukaryotic groups: TSA-FISH counts of each group were at the numerator and
256 total DAPI counts at the denominator.

257 *Abundance of specific picoeukaryotic taxa*

258 We used TSA-FISH to estimate the total abundance of six groups of picoeukaryotes,
259 chosen because they were well represented in the sequencing datasets of the picoplankton
260 from the studied samples (and poorly represented in the nanoplankton, Table S1). They
261 belonged to different eukaryotic supergroups: the Stramenopiles (MAST clades and
262 Pelagophyceae), Alveolates (the parasite clade MALV-II), Archaeplastida (*Micromonas* spp.)
263 and Rhizaria (*Minorisa minuta*). The taxonomic coverage of the used probes varied from
264 being very narrow targeting a species (*Minorisa minuta*) or a constrained phylogenetic clade
265 (*Micromonas* spp. and the MAST lineages), to being very wide targeting an algal class
266 (Pelagophyceae) or the diverse MALV-II group (formed by 44 phylogenetic clades). The sum
267 of heterotrophic cells (MASTs, *M. minuta* and MALV-II) represented on average 36% of
268 heterotrophic picoeukaryotes counted by DAPI, whereas the phototrophic cells targeted
269 (*Micromonas* and Pelagophyceae) represented on average only 22% of phototrophic
270 picoeukaryotes (Table 1).

271 The cell abundance of the six targeted groups varied strongly among the different
272 samples (Table S2). We found *Micromonas*, MAST-4, MAST-7 and MALV-II as the most
273 abundant taxa (averaged cell abundances of 1492, 279, 160, and 127 cells ml⁻¹, respectively),
274 detected in all samples. *Minorisa minuta* was very abundant in some sites, but absent in
275 others. By contrast, Pelagophyceae was the least abundant taxa (averaged cell abundances of
276 59 cells ml⁻¹). These cell counts pointed out that each sample contained a different

277 community. *Micromonas* was the most abundant taxa in 7 samples, MAST-4 in 4 samples and
278 *Minorisa* and MALV-II in the other two samples (Table S2).

279 *In-silico validation of the FISH probes against raw V4-reads*

280 Before applying TSA-FISH, we evaluated the effectiveness of the probes against the
281 V4-reads obtained from the same samples. This analysis was done with raw reads (extracted
282 from the initial dataset by using GenBank sequences of each group as search templates) to
283 take into account all sequence variants. The number of raw reads per group obtained from this
284 way was very similar to the number derived from the OTU table (Table 2). About 1000 to
285 3000 reads were extracted per group (except for MALV-II, about 30,000 reads). Then, we
286 calculated the percentage of raw reads having a 100% match with the probes (Table 2). The
287 five specific probes validated this way retrieved a very high percentage of reads, more than
288 95% in all cases except in MALV-II (83%). Therefore, the vast majority of reads from these
289 five groups in our samples had the target region of the probes.

290 The probe targeting *Micromonas* was not designed at the V4 region of the 18S rDNA,
291 so it could not be directly evaluated with V4-reads from this study. Therefore, we took the
292 OTUs affiliating to *Micromonas* (7 OTUs and 11,166 reads), retrieved the closest GenBank
293 complete sequence from these OTUs (nearly identical at the V4 region), and verified the
294 effectiveness of the probe against these 7 GenBank sequences. Only 3 sequences (accounting
295 for 30% of the reads) exhibited a perfect match, whereas the remaining 4 sequences had a
296 mismatch in the first position of the probe. Thus, probe MICRO01 could be improved perhaps
297 removing the first base, but since this mismatch is located in the first position it likely does
298 not affect the FISH counts.

299

300 ***Comparison of group specific read abundance and TSA-FISH counts***

301 The relative abundance of 454 V4-reads (from DNA and cDNA templates) and
302 illumina V9-reads (from cDNA templates) of each group of interest was compared with the
303 relative cell abundance assessed by epifluorescence microscopy (specific TSA-FISH counts
304 relative to total DAPI counts) in 13 samples for the V4-reads, and 9 samples for the V9-reads
305 (DCM samples from Naples and Oslo were excluded) (Fig. 2). The statistics of these plots are
306 shown in Table 3. For the DNA-V4, the correlation of the relative abundance of cells and
307 DNA reads was significant for all groups ($p < 0.05$) except for MAST-4 and Pelagophyceae,
308 and the goodness of these correlations varied among groups, being strongest for *Minorisa*
309 *minuta* ($R^2 = 0.97$) and weakest for MALV-II ($R^2 = 0.29$). Despite these good correlations,
310 linear slopes of the plots were always different from 1 except in MAST-7. In most cases
311 slopes were below 0.5, indicating an underestimation of cell abundance by 454 reads, while in
312 MALV-II the slope was very high (4.46), indicating a severe overestimation of the molecular
313 signal in this group.

314 By contrast, the correlations between relative cell and read abundances in the cDNA-
315 V4 survey were generally better for all groups, being also significant for Pelagophyceae and
316 MAST-4 (Table 3). Similar to the DNA-V4 survey, each group had a different slope, but in
317 this case there were three taxa (MAST-7, *M. minuta* and *Micromonas*) with slopes statistically
318 not different from 1, indicating that their relative abundances obtained by cell counts and 454
319 reads were comparable. In the six groups analysed, the slopes obtained in the cDNA survey
320 were closer to 1 than the slopes derived from the DNA survey, showing a better performance
321 of the cDNA approach.

322 For the Illumina cDNA-V9 survey, the correlations were slightly worse than for the
323 cDNA-V4 survey (Fig. 2, Table 3), as they were non-significant ($p > 0.05$) for MAST-4 and

324 MAST-7. Regarding the linear slopes, the three groups with a good performance at the
325 cDNA-V4 survey –*M. minuta*, Pelagophyceae and *Micromonas*– had slopes statistically
326 different from 1, indicating that in these groups the V4 region (and not the V9) could be used
327 as a proxy of cell counts. On the contrary, MALV-II had a better correlation with the V9-
328 cDNA reads than with the V4-reads, and its slope was not statistically different from one.
329 This highlights that there is not a "best region" that applies to all taxa.

330 *Differences when targeting V4 and V9 regions of the 18S rDNA*

331 To discard that the differences observed between the V4 and the V9 regions were due
332 to the use of different sequencing platforms (454 for V4 and Illumina for V9), we sequenced
333 with Illumina (MiSeq platform) the V4 region of one sample of the dataset (Oslo-2009 DCM)
334 using both templates (DNA and cDNA). The relative abundance of ~60 taxonomic groups
335 inferred from the same targeted region (V4) in the two platforms displayed a very good
336 agreement, with R^2 of 0.97 and 0.91 (for DNA and cDNA, respectively), and linear slopes of
337 0.92 to 1.02. Both slopes were not significantly different from 1. Furthermore, this analysis
338 was also done in an additional set of 14 samples (from other planktonic size fractions and
339 sediments; data not shown) and both platforms performed similarly, with R^2 ranging from
340 0.57 to 1.00 (average of 0.91) and slopes ranging from 0.73 to 1.21 (average of 0.99).
341 Therefore, sequencing the same 18S rDNA region with 454 or Illumina (MiSeq) gave highly
342 consistent results.

343 Therefore, the differences outlined above between V4-454 and V9-Illumina
344 sequencing (Table 3) were due to targeting different 18S rDNA regions and not due to the
345 sequencing platform. In order to observe these differences in more detail, we compared the
346 relative abundance of cDNA-V4 reads and cDNA-V9 reads for the six picoeukaryotic taxa
347 studied here (Fig. 3). Clear and consistent differences were identified in each case. As before,

348 the correlations were good and significant, with R^2 ranging from 0.68 to 0.98 (being MALV-
349 II lower, 0.45), but the slopes deviated significantly from 1 ($p < 0.05$). The V9 analysis
350 increased significantly the relative abundance of the stramenopile groups (the two MAST
351 clades and Pelagophyceae), with slopes ranging from 2.3 to 3.4 while it was the opposite for
352 *Micromonas* and MALV-II (slope of 0.2 and 0.3, respectively) and the same for *Minorisa*
353 *minuta* (slope of 1.1).

354

355 **Discussion**

356 Identifying marine picoeukaryotes by direct microscopy is problematic because of
357 their small sizes, and as a consequence there is an increasing interest in using high-throughput
358 sequencing (HTS) technologies to explore their diversity. HTS surveys provide a detailed
359 picture of the taxa present in the community, including rare species in the assemblage (18,
360 33), and reveal diversity not evident using other methods. However, the interpretation of the
361 HTS signal in terms of total cell abundances is not straightforward. Interestingly, TSA-FISH
362 is able to bridge microscopic and sequencing approaches by using specific phylogenetic
363 probes to estimate true cell abundances (28, 45). FISH, besides being very laborious, is also
364 limited by the number of taxa-specific probes available as well as by their phylogenetic
365 resolution (46). Moreover, TSA-FISH could be inaccurate due to putative mismatches of the
366 probes with the target group, which would result in cell counts underestimates. We addressed
367 this issue by evaluating the six probes against sequences obtained from the same samples, and
368 found an acceptable performance (very good in four cases, 83% of reads for MALV-II and
369 only one terminal mismatch for *Micromonas*). This validated that the TSA-FISH cell counts
370 performed here were accurate and enabled the main objective of this study, which was to

371 evaluate how well the HTS signal estimates community structure in terms of specific
372 abundance.

373 *More sequences imply more cells*

374 Since the HTS signal is always relative (number of reads of a given taxa respect to the
375 total read number), we needed the total picoeukaryote abundance to calculate relative cell
376 abundances. In principle, using TSA-FISH with a universal eukaryotic probe would be
377 consistent with the study and would also provide an extra layer of certainty, since it allows an
378 easier differentiation of eukaryotic cells from fluorescent particles and large bacteria.
379 However, TSA-FISH counts systematically resulted in fewer cells than direct DAPI counts,
380 and we noticed protists that were not labeled with the EUK502 probe. Moreover, this
381 discrepancy was particularly critical in samples dominated by very small cells. The wide size
382 spectra of protist cells in natural samples implied a large variation in the fluorescent signal, so
383 small cells with dim fluorescence may remain unnoticed when close to large fluorescent cells,
384 and easily faded away while counting a field having many cells with diverse sizes and
385 morphologies. This problem did not happen when using specific probes, since then we
386 focused in counting a defined cell type (even with dim fluorescence). Therefore, we used the
387 direct DAPI counts to calculate relative cell abundances.

388 When comparing the relative abundance of HTS reads against the relative cell
389 abundance obtained by TSA-FISH for the different taxa, we generally found a good
390 correlation between both methods. The R^2 coefficients of each picoeukaryotic taxa were
391 similar in the three comparisons conducted (DNA-V4, cDNA-V4 and cDNA-V9 vs. TSA-
392 FISH), except a very poor correlation for Pelagophyceae in the DNA-V4 survey.
393 Nevertheless, the statistical significance was always better for the cDNA survey than for the
394 DNA. These correlations imply that relative read abundance was proportional to relative cell

395 abundance, i.e. an increase in the HTS signal from a particular taxon is the result of an
396 increase of the proportion of targeted cells in the sample. However, the correlation
397 coefficients were far from 1 in most cases, and this noisy signal was probably related to
398 molecular biases plus the large differences in the picoeukaryotic composition of each sample.

399 Molecular surveys based on a single gene are affected by the widely discussed PCR
400 biases (47). During PCR, some phylotypes can be amplified preferentially, some groups can
401 remain undetected due to primer mismatches (48) or there could be biases due to the number
402 of PCR cycles (49). So, it has been suggested that the relative read abundance can no longer
403 reflect the real composition of the original community, biasing diversity estimates and
404 producing over or underestimations of specific groups (2). Furthermore, sequencing errors
405 may create false or chimeric taxa (16, 50, 51). Our results indicate that PCR biases and
406 putative sequencing artifacts are not affecting proportionality between relative read and cell
407 abundance: more reads imply high proportion of cells. The significant correlations detected
408 here using this sample dataset, where each sample has large differences in the picoeukaryotic
409 composition because they were taken in distant sites and times of the year, justifies the use of
410 relative read abundance as a proxy of community composition for comparative purposes.

411 ***Relative abundances of sequences and cells often disagree***

412 Despite the significant correlations discussed above, HTS and TSA-FISH surveys did
413 not give the same quantitative information, as often the regression line was statistically
414 different from 1. Moreover, these slopes varied strongly among the three HTS surveys. In
415 order to compare these surveys, we analyzed the relative abundances of the six picoeukaryotic
416 groups (among themselves) in the different samples (Fig. 4). This showed a general
417 agreement between TSA-FISH and the two cDNA surveys, but depending on the composition
418 of the sample, the agreement was better using the V4 region or the V9 region. In samples

419 dominated by *Micromonas* (e.g Blanes, Oslo-2010, Roscoff, Varna DCM), the picture
420 obtained with the V4 region matched better the cell abundance, while in samples dominated
421 by stramenopiles (MAST-4, MAST-7, Pelagophyceae), the V9 region performed better. In
422 our samples, the cDNA-V4 survey gives a better representation of the true species
423 composition for 5 of the samples while cDNA-V9 performed better in 4 of the samples.

424 In all cases, the DNA survey gave a more biased perspective of the relative abundance
425 of the 6 picoeukaryotic taxa, being influenced by a very high abundance of MALV-II reads in
426 all samples. This is probably due to a particularly high number of rDNA-operon copies in
427 MALV groups (2, 30, 32). The SSU rDNA copy number can vary orders of magnitude among
428 protist taxa, from few copies per cell in some green algae (52) to about 30 copies in MAST-4
429 (53) or several thousand copies in some dinoflagellates (52), depending on the cell size and
430 genome size (54). Large differences in the copy number of the targeted gene will affect the
431 abundance estimates in DNA surveys (2). Moreover, reads retrieved in DNA surveys could
432 derive from dead organisms or dissolved extracellular DNA. It is known that dissolved DNA
433 is preserved in marine waters (55), escaping from degradation and persisting for different
434 periods of time, from hours to days (56). On the contrary, reads from cDNA surveys derive
435 from ribosomes and represent metabolically active taxa in the community, as ribosomes are
436 needed to perform the RNA translation in metabolically active cells (57, 58). This, in addition
437 to the SSU rDNA copy number, could explain the differences observed between DNA and
438 cDNA surveys. Moreover, our data also highlighted the impact of targeting different regions
439 of the 18S rDNA gene for estimating relative abundances. For example, the cDNA-V9 survey
440 showed a higher signal (more reads) for MAST taxa and a lower signal for *Micromonas* when
441 compared with cDNA-V4. It is known that the range of taxonomic groups detected by V4 and
442 V9 is different (38, 59, 60) and that some groups can be over- or underrepresented. In
443 particular, in our samples the V4 region gives good estimates of cell counts for MAST-7 and

444 *Micromonas* spp., the V9 for MALV-II, and both regions for *Minorisa minuta*. So, the region
445 targeted (and the primers used) is fundamental to interpret any existing molecular data.

446 **Concluding remarks**

447 To our knowledge, this is the first study investigating the correspondence between
448 HTS and cell counts for selected and relevant taxa of marine picoeukaryotes. Indeed, true cell
449 abundances of picoeukaryotic taxa require the TSA-FISH approach, but as this approach has
450 inherent limitations (is time consuming, few probes are available, fine resolution can not be
451 provided), we see the need to pursue with HTS studies. Our results indicate a good correlation
452 between both methods, implying that more cells results in more sequences, although they give
453 different quantitative information, i.e. the relative read abundance cannot be directly related to
454 relative cell abundance. The cDNA-V4 survey showed the best agreement with TSA-FISH
455 abundance, providing 1:1 relationships in half of the assayed taxa, but the cDNA-V9 was best
456 for other taxa. So, the region of the 18S rDNA gene targeted clearly affected the relative
457 abundance of specific taxa. Finally, based in the data mentioned here, we suggest that the
458 sequencing platform used (454 or Illumina) does not produce major biases in diversity. In
459 conclusion, the most quantitative option is to use cDNA templates rather than DNA, while the
460 choice of the targeted region will result in different relative abundances in each particular
461 taxa.

462

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473

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475

476

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661

662 **Figure legends**

663 **Fig. 1.** Comparison of total picoeukaryotic abundance (cells <3 μm) by DAPI counts and
664 TSA-FISH counts using the eukaryotic probe EUK502 in all planktonic samples.

665 **Fig. 2.** Comparison of relative abundance of HTS reads against TSA-FISH cell counts in the
666 13 planktonic samples (9 samples for cDNA-V9 reads) for six picoeukaryotic taxa: MAST-4
667 (a), MAST-7 (b), *Minorisa minuta* (c), Pelagophyceae (d), *Micromonas* spp. (e) and MALV-
668 II (f). Dark blue symbols indicate DNA-V4 reads, light blue cDNA-V4 reads and green
669 cDNA-V9 reads. Regression lines are shown, and their statistics are presented in Table 3.

670 **Fig. 3.** Comparison of relative abundance of V9-Illumina reads and V4-454 reads (cDNA
671 surveys in both cases) in 9 planktonic samples for six picoeukaryote taxa: MAST-4 (a),
672 MAST-7 (b), *Minorisa minuta* (c), Pelagophyceae (d), *Micromonas* spp. (e) and MALV-II (f).

673 **Fig. 4.** Relative abundance of the different groups (among themselves) shown by the four
674 approaches (TSA-FISH, cDNA-V4, DNA-V4, cDNA-V9) in all planktonic samples. Gray
675 bars indicate the absence of the sample.

676

Fig. 1- Comparison of total picoeukaryotic abundance (cells <3 μm) by DAPI counts and TSA-FISH counts using the eukaryotic probe EUK502 in all planktonic samples.

Fig. 2- Comparison of relative abundance of HTS reads against TSA-FISH cell counts in the 13 planktonic samples (9 samples for cDNA-V9 reads), for six picoeukaryotic taxa: MAST-4 (a), MAST-7 (b), *Minorisa minuta* (c), Pelagophyceae (d), *Micromonas* spp. (e) and MALV-II (f). Dark blue symbols indicate DNA-V4 reads, light blue cDNA-V4 reads and green cDNA-V9 reads. Regression lines are shown, and their statistics are presented in Table 3.

Fig. 3 - Comparison of relative abundance of V9-illumina reads and V4-454 reads (cDNA surveys in both cases) in 9 planktonic samples for six picoeukaryote taxa: MAST-4 (a), MAST-7 (b), *Minorisa minuta* (c), Pelagophyceae (d), *Micromonas* spp. (e) and MALV-II (f).

Fig. 4 - Relative abundance of the different groups (among themselves) shown by the four approaches (TSA-FISH, cDNA-V4, DNA-V4, cDNA-V9) in all planktonic samples. Gray bars indicate the absence of the sample.

Table 1. Planktonic samples analyzed (sampling site, date, depth and seawater temperature) and cell counts (cells ml⁻¹) in these samples: total picoeukaryote abundance (cells ≤3 μm) determined by DAPI (phototrophs and heterotrophs), and photosynthetic picoeukaryote abundance determined by flow cytometry (FC). The last two columns show the percentage of phototrophic and heterotrophic cells explained by the probes used.

Sampling site	Date	Depth (m)	Temp. (°C)	DAPI counts		FC counts	%	%
				Phototr.	Heterotr.	Phototr.	Phototr.	Heterotr.
Blanes	Feb. 2010	1 (Surf.)	12.5	9273	445	9215	48.6	53.7
Gijon	Sep. 2010	1 (Surf.)	20.2	1606	2503	2990	14.5	20.2
Naples	Oct. 2009	1 (Surf.)	22.8	*	*	2714	-	-
		26 (DCM)	22.4	*	*	2049	-	-
Oslo	May 2010	1 (Surf.)	19.2	4376	4372	4700	1.1	54.6
		34 (DCM)	15.5	1808	1331	1802	8.3	28.8
		1 (Surf.)	15.0	12342	4470	9540	12.4	21.9
Roscoff	Sep. 2009	20 (DCM)	15.0	8773	2807	8930	17.9	38.4
		1 (Surf.)	15.0	7727	2893	13295	25.5	7.9
		10 (DCM)	12.5	21523	2823	17900	22.9	40.7
Roscoff	Apr. 2010	1 (Surf.)	9.9	7203	1034	8240	43.9	68.9
Varna	May 2010	1 (Surf.)	21.5	*	*	3861	-	-
		40 (DCM)	9.5	7043	731	9487	24.9	24.6

* DAPI counts were not performed, so picoeukaryotes could not be differentiated between phototrophs and heterotrophs. In these samples, total picoeukaryote counts were done on FISH filters and were: 4272 cells ml⁻¹ in Naples-2009 Surf, 1834 cells ml⁻¹ in Naples-2009 DCM, and 4656 cells ml⁻¹ in Varna Surf. These values were used in the correlations.

Table 2. List of oligonucleotide FISH probes used and effectiveness of the probes against reads from this study (% reads-probe). The table shows the number of 454 reads from each phylogenetic group extracted from the OTU table or from raw reads by local BLAST. The last column shows the percentage of raw reads in each group that have the probe target region with 0 mismatches.

Probe Name	Target group	Probe sequence (5' – 3')	Probe reference	Num. of reads per Taxa		% reads - probe
				In OTU table	From the raw reads	
NS4	MAST-4	TACTTCGGTCTGCAAACC	Massana <i>et al.</i> , 2002	2082	2082	98.0
NS7	MAST-7	TCATTACCATAGTACGCA	This study	2842	2833	95.7
CRN02	<i>Minorisa minuta</i>	TACTTAGCTCTCAGAACC	del Campo <i>et al.</i> , 2012	1853	1853	99.8
PELA01	Pelagophyceae	ACGTCCTTGTTGACGCT	Not <i>et al.</i> , 2002	4440	3169	98.5
MICRO01	<i>Micromonas</i> spp.	AATGGAACACCGCCGGCG	Not <i>et al.</i> , 2004	11,166	-	-
ALV01	MALV-II	GCCTGCCGTGAACACTCT	Chambouvet <i>et al.</i> , 2008	35,359	29,894	83.0
EUK502	Eukaryotes	GCACCAGACTTGCCCTCC	Lim <i>et al.</i> , 1999	-	-	-

Table 3. Statistics (R^2 , slope value, and p-value) of the correlations between relative abundance of reads and cells in the three molecular surveys: 454 DNA-V4 (Fig. 2, dark blue), 454 cDNA-V4 (Fig. 2, light blue) and Illumina cDNA-V9 (Fig. 2, green). The fourth statistics (p1) compares the slopes against the desired value of 1 (i.e. "ns" indicates that the slope is not significantly different from 1).

	V4 - 454 survey								V9 - Illumina survey			
	DNA				cDNA				cDNA			
	R^2	slope	p-value	p1	R^2	slope	p-value	p1	R^2	slope	p-value	p1
MAST-4	0.18	0.14	ns	-	0.31	0.21	*	***	0.3	0.84	ns	-
MAST-7	0.33	0.75	*	ns	0.31	1.16	*	ns	0.36	2.79	ns	-
<i>Minorisa minuta</i>	0.97	0.24	***	***	0.98	1.01	***	ns	0.99	1.13	***	***
Pelagophyceae	0.06	0.14	ns	-	0.94	2.78	***	***	0.68	5.68	**	**
<i>Micromonas</i> spp.	0.87	0.47	***	***	0.73	0.83	***	ns	0.87	0.2	***	***
MALV-II	0.29	4.46	*	*	0.39	1.68	*	*	0.60	0.89	*	ns

Significance codes: ***: <0.001; **: 0.001–0.01; *: 0.01–0.05; ns: no significant